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PHASE EQUILIBRIUM IN THE CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 SYSTEM AND ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE CaInTe_2 COMPONENT

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Abstract

The physicochemical properties of alloys of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system and the electrical properties of the CaInTe_2 compound were studied by complex methods of physicochemical analysis: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray phase analysis (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as the determination of microhardness and density, the phase diagram of the system was built. The phase diagram of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system is partially quasi-binary. Eutectic equilibrium and peritectic transformation occur in the system. In the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system, only on the side of the CaIn_2Te_4 compound, solid solutions reach 8 mol. % CaInTe_2 , solid solutions based on CaInTe_2 are practically not found. The electro-physical properties of the CaInTe_2 compound have been studied.

Keywords. system, density, microhardness, phase, solid solution

Introduction

The components of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system were synthesized by the ampoule method from CaTe , InTe and In_2Te_3 compounds. The properties of the elements of the main II subgroup are given in detail by the author of [1]. In systems with the presence of calcium, semiconductor materials with luminescent properties were studied in [2, 3]. Indium chalcogenides and the ternary and quaternary phases and solid solutions derived from them are semiconductor materials with functional properties. Indium sulfide and selenide compounds are photoelectric [4–8], and telluride compounds are semiconductors with thermoelectric properties [9,10]. From this point of view, the study of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system is of scientific and practical importance.

The purpose of the work is to study the phase equilibrium in the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system, build its phase diagram and study the electrical properties of the CaInTe_2 compound.

Experimental part

Alloys of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system were synthesized from CaInTe_2 and CaIn_2Te_4 components in evacuated quartz ampoules up to a pressure of 0.133 Pa. The alloys were synthesized in the temperature range 1100–1400 K. For homogenization, the alloys were

subjected to heat treatment at 610 K for 240 hours. Then the samples were studied by the methods of physicochemical analysis (DTA, XRF, MSA, measurements of density and microhardness).

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the alloys was carried out on an NTR-73 low-frequency pyrometer. Chromel-alumel was taken as a thermocouple, the heating rate was 10 K/min.

X-ray phase analysis (XPA) was performed on a D2 PASER X-ray diffractometer. At that time, $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a Ni filter were used. The microstructure of the samples was analyzed using a MIM-8 microscope.

The microhardness of the alloys was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic microscope. The density of the samples was determined by the pycnometric method; toluene was taken as the working solution. The electrical properties of the CaInTe_2 compound were carried out in vacuum by the compensation method [11,12].

Results and its discussion

Of great interest are the physicochemical and physical properties of ternary and more complex compounds of calcium with other metals. Therefore, the study of the chemical interaction of CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 in the internal section of the Ca-In-Te ternary

system is one of the important issues. Synthesis of alloys of the system was carried out from the CaInTe_2 and CaIn_2Te_4 components by the ampoule method under a vacuum of 0.133 Pa. The resulting alloys are compact black substances. The alloys were subjected to heat treatment for 300 hours at 400°C to homogenize them.

Components CaInTe_2 and CaIn_2Te_4 are gradually triturated during prolonged exposure to the open air. The reason for this is that when exposed to air, they gradually absorb moisture from the air and undergo changes. Alloys of the system dissolve very well in strong mineral acids (HCl , HNO_3). Homogenized samples were studied by the methods of physicochemical analysis.

During the differential thermal analysis of alloys of the $\text{CaInTe}_2 - \text{CaIn}_2\text{Te}_4$ system, it was found that more than two endothermic effects are observed on their thermograms. A large number of effects on thermograms indicates that a complex interaction occurs in the system. The results of the microstructure analysis show that the alloys of the system in the solid state are single-phase and two-phase. Since the CaInTe_2 compound is peritectic in the system and as a result of the decomposition of this compound at high temperatures, three-phase fields are also present.

Fig. 1. X-ray patterns of alloys of the $\text{CaInTe}_2 - \text{CaIn}_2\text{Te}_4$ system.
1- CaInTe_2 , 2-40 mol %, 3-70 mol %, 4- 100 mol.% CaIn_2Te_4 .

Fig. 2. Phase diagram of the $\text{CaInTe}_2 - \text{CaIn}_2\text{Te}_4$ system.

Based on the CaIn_2Te_4 compound, a sufficient area of the solid solution is formed. To refine the region of the solid solution, alloys containing 3, 5, 7, and 8 mol % CaInTe_2 , which were kept at 200 and 400 °C for 150 hours, were subjected to heat treatment and cooling by placing them in ice water at these temperatures. After that, microstructural analysis of samples containing 3, 5, 7 and 8 mol. % CaInTe_2 . As a result, it was found that the solubility region at room temperature based on the CaIn_2Te_4 compound is 8 mol % CaInTe_2 . At the eutectic temperature, the region of the solid solution based on CaIn_2Te_4 corresponds to an interval of 15 mol % CaInTe_2 .

In order to confirm the results of differential thermal and microstructural analyzes, an X-ray phase analysis of alloys with 40 and 70 mol % CaIn_2Te_4 of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system (Fig.1). According to the results of X-ray analysis, it was found that the diffraction lines obtained on the diffraction patterns of the alloys consist of a mixture of diffraction lines of the primary components. That is, the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system has a quasi-binary character in the solid state. At higher temperatures, the system is partially quasi-binary. As a result, the results of the analyzes complement each other.

By measuring the microhardness of the phases of the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system, a comparison was made of the components that make up the system. As a result of measuring the microhardness in the system, two types of values were determined. The microhardness value (1650-1750) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the CaInTe_2 compound, and the value (1900-1990) MPa corresponds to the microhardness value of the α -solid solution based on the CaIn_2Te_4 compound.

Based on the results of physicochemical analysis, a phase diagram of the system was constructed (Fig. 2). The state diagram of the system is partially quasi-binary, accompanied by eutectic equilibrium and peritectic transformations.

The liquidus of the system is limited by the monovariant equilibrium curves of the α -solid solution formed on the basis of the CaIn_2Te_4 and CaInTe_2 compound, which is in equilibrium with the liquid. In the range of 0-70 mol % CaIn_2Te_4 , as a result of the decomposition of the CaInTe_2 compound, two-phase regions consisting of $M + \text{CaTe}$ are observed below the liquidus curve. Another two-phase region consists of $(M + \alpha)$ below the liquidus curve in the region of 70-100 mol % CaIn_2Te_4 . As a result of reprecipitation, three-phase fields arise in the concentration range of 0-85 mol % CaIn_2Te_4 from $(M + \text{CaTe} + \text{CaInTe}_2)$ and $M + \alpha + \text{CaIn}_2\text{Te}_4$. The region of the α -solid solution formed on the basis of the CaIn_2Te_4 compound is 8 mol % CaInTe_2 .

Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity (σ), thermo-EMF (α), current strength (I) and resistivity (ρ) of the CaInTe_2 compound were studied in the temperature range of 300-350 K. The dimensions of the samples were 1.5x0.5x0.4 cm.

The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity (σ) of the CaInTe_2 compound is shown in fig. 3. It can be seen from the graph that the electrical conductivity increases with temperature. Additional conductivity occurs in the temperature range of 300-350 K, the specific conductivity is formed with a subsequent increase in temperature. The electrical conductivity of the CaInTe_2 compound at room temperature is $\sigma = 2.96 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$, and at 350 K it is $\sigma = 4.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. The CaInTe_2 compound also has a relatively high resistivity.

The thermo-EMF of this compound is also given in fig. 3. The thermo-EMF of the CaInTe_2 compound decreases with temperature. The value of its thermoelectric coefficient at room temperature $\alpha = 620 \mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$, and at 350 K its value is $\alpha = 350 \mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$.

Fig.3. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity and thermo-EMF of the CaInTe_2

Fig.4. Temperature dependence of the electric current (a) and resistivity (b) of the CaInTe_2 compound.

On fig. 4 a shows the temperature dependence of the current strength of the CaInTe_2 compound. The CaInTe_2 compound has a lower resistance, so the temperature dependent increase in current flowing through the CaInTe_2 is large. The value of the current strength at room temperature is $I = 3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ A, and at 350 K $I = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ A. An increase in the current strength depending on temperature indicates that the CaInTe_2 compound has a semiconductor property.

The temperature dependence of the resistivity of the CaInTe_2 compound is shown in fig. 4 b. As can be seen from the temperature dependence of resistivity, the temperature dependence is linear and decreases with temperature. The resistivity of the CaInTe_2 compound is significantly lower than the resistivity of the CaInSe_2 compound. The reason for this is related to the increase in the proportion of metallic bonds in the series $\text{Se} \rightarrow \text{Te}$. The resistivity of the CaInSe_2 and CaInTe_2 compounds is $\rho = 75 \cdot 10^8 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ and $\rho = 3 \cdot 10^7 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, respectively.

Conclusion

The chemical interaction in the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system was studied by the methods of physicochemical analysis and its phase diagram was constructed. As a result of the decomposition of the CaInTe_2 compound, the state diagram of the system becomes partially quasi-binary. The process of eutectic equilibrium and peritectic transformation takes place in the system. In the CaInTe_2 - CaIn_2Te_4 system at room temperature, solid solutions based on CaIn_2Te_4 reach up to 8 mol % CaInTe_2 and on the basis of the CaInTe_2 compound, the solid solution region is practically not defined. The temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity (σ), thermo-EMF (α), current strength (I), and resistivity (ρ) of the CaInTe_2 compound has been studied in the temperature range of 20–150°C.

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